

A Study of Brucine and O-Phenylenediamine Complexes of Blue Perchromate (Prepared with Citric Acid)

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Blue perchromate was prepared in presence of citric acid. Different samples of brucine and O-Phenylenediamine complexes with this blue perchromate were prepared and studied. Analytical data suggest that the complexes contain trivalent chromium along with hexavalent chromium. Magnetic susceptibility measurements also supports the above view. The magnetic moment values for brucine and O-Phenylenediamine complexes were found to be 3.904 B. M. and 3.938 B. M. respectively which correspond to the presence of three unpaired electrons. The study supports Rai's formula for the blue perchromate.

COMPLEXES of the blue perchromate with different nitrogenous bases have been studied by different workers¹⁻⁶. Rai and co-workers (loc. cit) prepared pyridine, piperidine, 8-hydroxy quinoline, quinoline and strychnine complexes of the blue perchromate and suggested the presence of Cr(III) along with Cr(VI) in them. Rajput, Govil and Singhal⁷ and Tomar, Singh and Singh⁸ supported the view put forward by Rai and co-workers. Blue perchromate can be prepared by using different acids (such as sulphuric acid phthalic acid, tartaric acid, succinic acid, etc.). In the present communication the blue perchromate was prepared in presence of citric acid.

This blue perchromate has been assigned⁹, $(Cr_3A_2)[Cr(Cr_2O_{10})_3]$ formula (where A represents citrate ion). Different samples of brucine and O-phenylenediamine complexes with this blue perchromate were prepared and studied.

Experimental

Ethereal blue perchromate prepared with citric acid :

This sample was prepared by mixing ice-cold solutions of 5% (W/V) $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (50 ml.), $N/2$ citric acid (60 ml.) and 6% H_2O_2 (10 ml.). The blue compound thus formed was extracted with ice-cold ethyl ether (100 ml.). The ethereal solution of blue perchromate was separated, washed several times with ice-cold distilled water and placed in a tightly stoppered flask in a freezing mixture (ice and common salt) in order to freeze out the water. After about 15 min. the solution was transferred to a dry flask kept in ice.

Brucine complex : 50 ml. of 1% cold ethereal solution of brucine was added dropwise to 50 ml. cold ethereal blue perchromate. A dirty yellow ppt. was formed. After 2-3 hr. it was filtered, washed with ether to make the complex free from the base and dried in desiccator.

O-phenylenediamine complex : To 50 ml. cold ethereal blue perchromate, an excess of cold and saturated ethereal solution of O-phenylenediamine was added. A black ppt. was obtained, on keeping the mixture overnight. The ppt. was filtered and washed with ether till the filtrate was colourless. It was then dried in a desiccator.

Determination of oxidising powers of the complexes : Definite weights of the complexes were dissolved separately in minimum volume of $N-NaOH$ solution and the solution was made upto a definite volume with distilled water. Oxidising powers of the complexes were determined volumetrically as suggested by Tomar, Singh and Singh⁸.

Estimation of chromium in the basic part and determination of the oxidising power of the filtrate : Chromium in the basic part of the complexes was estimated (i) volumetrically and (ii) gravimetrically as described by Tomar, Singh and Singh (loc. cit). Oxidising power of the filtrate (obtained from gravimetric method) was also determined by the method suggested by the above workers. (The observations and the results have been given in Table 1).

TABLE 1—BRUCINE AND O-PHENYLENEDIAMINE COMPLEXES OF BLUE COMPOUND PREPARED WITH CITRIC ACID

Complexes.	Volume (ml.) of hypo solution used in titrating 25 ml. of			After precipitation of $Cr(OH)_3$ from (d), % of Cr in basic part.	% of Total Cr. (Gravimetrically)	Ratios.			
	(Z) solution without oxidation.	(Z) solution after oxidation	Filtrate of (Z) solution after pptns of $Cr(OH)_3$.			c/b	o/d	d/b	f/e
1. Brucine.	2.45	4.70	2.40	3.779	7.6980	1.91	1.95	0.97	2.03
	2.40	4.75	2.40	3.799	7.7451	1.97	1.97	1.00	2.03
2. O-phenylene-diamine.	2.25	4.50	2.30	6.066	12.4331	2.00	1.95	1.02	2.04
	2.20	4.45	2.25	6.062	12.4331	2.02	1.97	1.02	2.05

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TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA

Name of Complex.	Colour	Proposed formulae.	Percentage of elements.									
			Cr.		N		C		H		O	
			Cal.	Found.	Cal.	Found.	Cal.	Found.	Cal.	Found.	Cal.	Found.
Brucine	Yellow.	$R_2A_2Cr(CrO_{10})$	7.27	7.70	3.91	3.95	48.67	48.29	4.33	4.38	35.82	35.68
O-Phenylene-diamine.	Black.	$R_2A_2Cr(CrO_{10})$	12.12	12.42	6.50	6.98	33.52	33.90	3.03	3.20	44.83	43.50

Estimation of the elements: Chromium was estimated as Cr_2O_3 by igniting definite weights of the complexes in a silica crucible. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by combustion method. Amount of oxygen was determined by difference. The results have been given in Table 2.

Magnetic measurements: Magnetic susceptibility of all the complexes was determined by Gouy's method, and magnetic moments calculated.

Discussion

The titre values in Column 'b' and 'd' of Table 1 are the same (vide ratio d/b). The titre values in column 'c' are double the values shown in Columns 'b' and 'd' of this table (vide ratios c/b and c/d). Therefore Chromium is present in equal proportions in the acidic and basic parts of the complexes. This is further confirmed from the fact that the percentage of total chromium is double that of chromium obtained in the basic part of the complexes (vide column 'f' and the ratio f/ee).

It is evident from the Table 2 that the empirical formula for both the complexes formed from the blue per-chromate (prepared with citric acid) correspond to $RACrO_5$ (where R and A represent one molecule of each of the base and the citrate ion respectively).

The magnetic moment values for brucine and O-phenylenediamine complexes were found to be 3.904 B. M. and 3.938 B. M. respectively. These values correspond to the presence of three unpaired electrons and thus supports the presence of Cr(III).

The observations made with chemical and analytical studies along with their behaviour in magnetic field

clearly show that (1) Both the complexes contain equal amount of chromium in acidic and basic parts.

(ii) The base molecule and the citrate ions are attached to the blue perchromate molecule in both the complexes.

(iii) The probable molecular formula for both the complexes can be written as $R_2A_2Cr(CrO_{10})$ where R and A stand for base molecule and citrate ion respectively.

On examining the possibility of attachment of the base molecule and citrate ions in the two probable formulae for the blue perchromate i. e. CrO_5 and $Cr_2(Cr_2O_{10})_3$ it seems quite probable in the latter formula as it has the necessary Cr(III) for complex formation. The study of these complexes therefore, supports the Rai's formula, $Cr_2(Cr_2O_{10})_3$ for blue perchromate.

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